

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Dec, 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10965993

SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: THE CURRENT SITUATION OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT AND THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF PARTICIPATIVE MANAGEMENT TO SCHOOL SUCCESS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF DIAS D'AVILA – BAHIA

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ABSTRACT

The study addresses the current situation of school management and how it has been managed in its dimensions, investigating whether the contributions of participatory management interfere with the learning of 3rd year students and other school segments in the municipality of Dias d'Ávila - Bahia. The quantitative/qualitative heterogeneous method used with a factual approach described in the period of six months of the second half of 2016. Data collection obtained through a semi-structured questionnaire, involving ten questions, analyzing the low IDEB indexes; high dropout rates and failure rates among students enrolled in Regular High School. In the analysis of the results, a set of managerial situations was identified which contributed to the facts that occurred. Conclusion from the point of view of the investigated actors detects a traditionalist management practice, impacting the results of the pedagogical praxis, its high rate of failures and abandonment. The research suggests the experiment of participatory management as an empirical method, the creation of a nucleus for monitoring graduates in educational units, seeking to strengthen the school institution and student learning. Keywords: Situation. School. Participative management. Students. Challenges. Teaching-Learning.